

Tallinn Declaration

First Symposium of Deaf Interpreting and Translation

Tallinn University, Estonian Sign Language Research Lab / WASLI Region Europe

[International Sign Language version](#)

There is a rapidly growing number of Deaf interpreters and translators in many European countries. At the same time, they are facing several structural challenges in the field of Sign Language interpreting and translation. We must find common ground in understanding the nature of both the interpreting and the translating professions while building a sense of cooperation through teamwork

In the context of the increasing number of professional Deaf interpreters and translators in Europe, it is crucial to define, review, and revise the current professional standards in sign language interpreting and translation. This will enable Deaf interpreters and Deaf translators to provide high-quality interpreting and translating services.

At this point, six key points in the area of professionalisation of Deaf interpreters and translators have been identified:

1. Providing training opportunities for future DI/Ts
2. Quality management of the interpreting and translation production
3. Equal employment opportunities
4. Establishment of transparent certification and registration procedures for DI/DTs
5. Representation of Deaf interpreters and Deaf translators in professional associations of sign language interpreters
6. Research into Deaf Interpreting and Translation

In addition, we recognise that there are issues that need to be explored in more detail:

1. Working with linguistically and culturally diverse Deaf communities
2. Good practice examples of diverse interpreting settings with Deaf interpreters in education, employment, emergency services, health, media, and conferences.
3. Standards for interpreting and translating productions in both National Sign Languages and International Sign Language.

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Finally, an open dialogue with Deaf and hearing interpreter and translator colleagues need to be continued and expanded with the overall goal of providing high-quality sign language interpreting and translating services.